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May we record?

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Thank you!

How development speed is impacted by the current way of working with requirements

1a. For your organization/department, development speed is impacted in the following ways:
Do you agree or disagree? Fill out table below.

Aspect	Impact on development speed	Reason	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Strongly disagree	No opinion
Requirements style dominated by safety and legal concerns	Negative	Neglects development speed						
Requirements-centric culture	Negative	Constrains development speed						
Rigid requirements process	Negative	Forces early decisions						
Focus on decomposition and hierarchy	Negative	Introduces delays						
Requirements representation	Negative	Hinders change						
Requirements-based contracts	Negative	Hinder fast collaboration						

1b. Any aspect to add? *Free text/speech response*

2a1. The impacts of the following aspects are being addressed with the Agile transformation:
Do you agree or disagree? Fill out table below.

Aspect	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Strongly disagree	No opinion
Requirements style dominated by safety and legal concerns						
Requirements-centric culture						
Rigid requirements process						
Focus on decomposition and hierarchy						
Requirements representation						
Requirements-based contracts						

2a2. Why is the aspect addressed or not addressed by the agile transformation?
Free text/speech response

2b. Any further comments? *Free text/speech response*

New aspects which should be considered when defining a new way of working with requirements to increase development speed

3a1. For your organization/department, the following aspects would increase development speed:

Do you agree or disagree? Fill out 3a1 in table below.

3a2. Would you agree or disagree to spend effort on these? Fill out 3a2 in table below.

Aspect	Impact on development speed	Reason	3a1					3a2					4a1				
			Strongly agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Strongly disagree	No opinion	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Strongly disagree	No opinion	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither
Domain- or context-specific requirements tooling	Positive	Improves specialization															
Model-driven requirements	Positive	Enables fast feedback															
Aligning requirements with automated testing	Positive	Increases trust and quality															
Emergent teams	Positive	Improve collaboration															
Facilitate exploration driven work	Positive	Facilitates learning															
Complement lightweight pre-development requirements with precise post-development specification	Positive	Reduces workload															

3b. Any aspect to add? Free text/speech response

4a1. The above aspects are covered as part the Agile transformation:

Do you agree or disagree? Fill out 4a1 in table above.

4a2. Why is the aspect addressed or not addressed by the agile transformation? Free text/speech response

4b. Any further comments? Free text/speech response